

Effect of in Ova Injection with Nano Selenium and Vitamin E on Hatch and Some Blood Biochemical Traits of Broiler Chicks Exposed to Fasting Condition

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Abstract:

This investigation in the hatchery operated by Al-Anwar Poultry Group in Babylon governorate utilized 750 fertilized eggs from January 15 to February 6, 2019. The eggs were partitioned into 5 groups, as follows: T1, serving as a negative control treatment without injection, and T2, serving as a positive control therapy injected with distilled water. Each group included 150 fertilized eggs. Treatments T5, T4, and T3 involved administering a nutritional solution comprising Nano- selenium coupled with vitamin E at dosages of 15-30-45 ppm, respectively, via injection. Subsequently, the chicks were isolated from the injected egg treatments, and each treatment was further divided into three repetitions. The chicks were then cultivated experimentally for 48 hours without any food and

were just provided with water. The subsequent outcomes were achieved: Treatment T3 showed a statistically significant difference ($P \leq 0.01$) in the relative hatchability percentage. The treatment T2 ($P \leq 0.01$) markedly outperformed the other treatments in terms of embryonic mortality percentage. There was also a significant excelled ($P \leq 0.05$) for the treatment T1 in the concentration of blood cholesterol and during times 0-12-24-48 hours after hatching, a significant excelled ($P \leq 0.05$) for the treatments T2, T1 in the concentration of triglycerides during the times 0-48 hours after hatching, and the treatment T2 excelled during the times 12-24 hours, a significant excelled ($P \leq 0.05$) for the treatment T2 in the concentration of glucose Blood when hatching, and T3 and T1 treatments excelled 12 hours, Treatment T2 at time 24 hours, and highly significant ($P \leq 0.01$) for T2 and T1 at 48 hours after hatching, significant difference ($P \leq 0.05$) for T5 in the concentration of GpX, was significant. Treatment T1 surpassed the established concentration of Malonaldehyde within the first 48 hours after hatching.

Keywords: *Early feeding, feed fasting, hatch rate, antioxidant.*

Introduction

The application of contemporary technology in genetics, biotechnology, and nanotechnology has greatly enhanced the poultry sector in the last four decades by Havenstein, et al. (2007) by promoting fast bird growth and efficient conversion of feeds. However, the formative stage of embryonic growth and development is still critical until hatching (Hulet, (2007)). It has been shown that the subsequent growth and weight of chicks during marketing depend on optimal growth during incubation and their weight at hatching. The third The survival duration of the chicks in the hatchery and until their transfer to the breeding houses is a notable concern. This is because the chicks may stay in the hatchery for a day or two without access to water or food, hence subjecting them to stress and resulting in weight loss and compromised immune systems. In order to enhance the level of immunity in chicks and raise their weight upon hatching, it is essential to use the technique of early feeding which involves injecting hatching eggs with solutions containing vitamins, minerals, and nutrients. Vitamin E is classified as a fat-soluble vitamin. There exist eight distinct forms of vitamin E, among which α -tocopherol holds the highest importance. This is attributed to its ability to be absorbed and metabolised by the body, its antioxidant characteristics that reduce the conversion of fats into peroxides and the damage caused by free radicals to cells, and its ability to enhance the activity and efficacy of the enzyme glutathione peroxidase, which functions to reduce the production of fatty peroxides (Herrera, & Barbas, 2001). due to its superior bioavailability and reduced toxicity relative to its inorganic and organic counterparts, where inorganic compounds are more harmful than organic substances Nano-selenium is garnering significant interest References 9 and 10. In addition to shielding cells from oxidation and oxidative stress-induced damage, nano-selenium also controls thyroid hormone levels, cell proliferation, and antioxidant defense mechanisms. It operates synergistically with α -tocopherol to achieve this effect. Gao, X., Zhang, J., & Zhang, L. (2002) spherical nano

selenium has demonstrated antioxidant properties that reduce the likelihood of selenium toxicity. Furthermore, it can serve as an antioxidant while reducing the likelihood of toxicity. Experimental results demonstrated that the introduction of nano-selenium and vitamin E into hatching eggs resulted in increased chick weight and increased glycogen content in the liver, abdominal muscle, and heart. The objective of this study is to determine the influence of early nutrition using a solution containing nutrients on the hatching rate, certain metabolic traits, and the levels of nano selenium and vitamin E in broiler chick Ross 308 that are subjected to feed fasting in the hatchery.

Materials and Methods

The laboratory experiment was conducted at the Al-Anwar Poultry Company hatchery located in the Babylon province between January 15, 2019, and February 6, 2019. On January 15, 2019, A total of 900 eggs had been weighed followed by incubated over 17.5 days. from embryo age. After the scanning candling process, 750 fertilized eggs were separated from the unfertilized eggs. For each treatment, 150 eggs were used. T1 served as a negative control therapy without injections, while T2 served regarding the positive control treatment including water that is distilled injections. Every participant was administered an injection of a nutritious solution enriched with nano-Selenium plus vitamin E at doses varying between 15 to 45 parts per million (ppm). The chicks being cultivated over a period of 48 hours after hatching, throughout which every treatment was at random divided into three replicates and given only water without any kind of nourishment.

Investigation of eggs and injection solutions

The eggs got from the hatchery of Al-Anwar Poultry Group and had an average weight of 58 and 60 grammes. A crucial vitamin E called α -Tocopherol, produced by the Indian business HIMEDIA, was obtained from the medical and veterinarian supply office located in Bab al-Muatham, Baghdad governorate.

Liquefied organically nano-selenium was obtained from the Iranian Nanosany Group.

Studied Traits

Percentage of hatching and embryonic mortality %

Calculated according to Khattab, Kassab, & Al-Taie, (1992).

Biochemical traits

The glucose was measure by use (Kit) from the German Roche company according to Coles, (1986), The cholesterol concentration was measure by use (Kit) from the German Roche company according to Franey, & Elias, (1968), and the concentration of triglycerides was measure by use (Kit) from the German Roche company according to Fossati, & Prencipe, (1982). As for the enzyme glutathione peroxidase, and malonaldehyde was measure by use (Kit) from the German Roche company according to Buege, & Aust, (1978).

Statistical Analysis

Use the statistical analysis according to the design (CRD) Duncan, (1955) & SAS Institute Inc. (2012) and use the mathematical model:

$$Y_{ij} = \mu + T_i + e_{ij} \quad (1)$$

Results and Discussion

Percentage of Hatching % and the Percentage of Embryonic Mortality %

The percentages of hatching and embryonic mortality are affected by early adding of nano-selenium and vitamin E into the diet, as shown in Table 1. It was discovered that the T3 treatment significantly outperformed the other treatments in terms of percentage of hatching ($P \leq 0.01$) as well as the T5 treatment on the T4, T2, T1, and the two treatments T4, T1 on the T2 treatment. However, there were no significant differences between the two treatments T4 and T1. Regarding the proportion of embryonic mortality, treatment T2 outperformed T4 and T1 treatments ($P \leq 0.01$) and provided the highest average percentage of embryonic death compared to the other treatments.

Table 1. Percentage of Hatching % and Percentage of Embryonic Mortality % in Broiler Chicks Feed Nano-Selenium, Vitamin E during Embryonic Stage

Treatments	Means \pm standard error	
	percentage of embryonic mortality %	percentage of Hatching %
T1	12.42 \pm 0.42 b	87.58 \pm 0.42 c
T2	16.40 \pm 0.93 a	83.59 \pm 0.93 d
T3	4.16 \pm 0.83 d	95.83 \pm 0.83 a
T4	12.39 \pm 0.73 b	87.60 \pm 0.72 c
T5	9.17 \pm 0.83 c	90.83 \pm 0.83 b
Significant level	**	**

Note: Significant differences exist among the various letters at the level ($P \geq 0.05$). Treatments T1, T2, T3, T4, and T5 were assigned numerical values representing a negative control treatment with no an injection, a positive control treatment with a water-distilled injection, and an injection of a nutritional solution containing vitamin E and nano- Selenium at concentrations of fifteen, thirty, and forty-five ppm.

Cholesterol Concentration (mg/100ml blood)

Table 2 demonstrates that the blood cholesterol levels of broiler chicks subjected to food fasting are influenced by hatching eggs that have been

injected with nano selenium and vitamin E. Statistically significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) were seen between treatment T1 and treatments T3, T4, and T5 during hatching. However, there were no significant differences between

treatment T2 and treatment T1, or between treatments T2, T3, T4, or T5. At 12 hours after hatching, T1 therapy significantly surpassed both T3 and T5 treatments ($P \geq 0.05$). T4 demonstrated superior performance compared

to T3 treatment, while T2 treatment above both T3 and T5 treatments. Furthermore, no noticeable distinction was observed between the T5 and T4 therapies or the T2 and T1 treatments.

Table 2. Cholesterol Level (mg / 100ml blood) in Broiler Chicks Feed Nano-Selenium, Vitamin E during Embryonic Stage

Treatments	Means \pm standard error			
	at hatching	12 hours	24 hours	48 hours
T1	2.44 \pm 1.33 a	238.76 \pm 2.39 a	244.16 \pm 1.69 a	251.84 \pm 1.35 a
T2	222.51 \pm 2.36 ab	234.79 \pm 3.62 ab	213.61 \pm 1.36 ab	212.07 \pm 2.94 ab
T3	198.33 \pm 1.18 b	205.14 \pm 5.01 c	204.41 \pm 2.26 ab	195.28 \pm 0.61 b
T4	187.15 \pm 3.02 b	213.09 \pm 1.90 b	209.45 \pm 1.20 ab	216.97 \pm 1.72 ab
T5	199.23 \pm 1.88 b	216.60 \pm 2.51 b	175.22 \pm 1.04 b	188.39 \pm 3.17 b
Significant	*	*	*	*

Note: Significant differences exist among the various letters at the level ($P \leq 0.05$). A negative control treatment with no injection and a positive control treatment involving injection of distilled water, Treatments T1, T2, T3, T4, and T5 comprised the injection of a nutrient solution containing vitamin E and nano- Selenium at concentrations of fifteen, thirty, and forty-five ppm.

Concentration of Triglycerides (mg/100ml blood)

Table (3) shows the impact on the triglyceride concentration in broiler chicks exposed to meal fasting of injecting nano selenium and vitamin E into viable eggs. When compared to the T2, T1, T5, T4, and T3 treatments, significant development was seen ($P \leq 0.05$) for the T2 and T1 treatments at hatching. T5, T4, T3, and T2

have a substantial difference from each other. During the period of time 12 hours after hatching, it was discovered that there were substantial differences ($P \leq 0.05$) between treatment T2 and the other transactions, as well as treatment T1's superiority over the two T5 and T4 treatments. There was no discernible change. Regarding the 24-hour period following hatching, between T3 and T1 treatments and between T5 and T4 treatments

Table 3. Triglycerides Level (mg / 100ml blood) in Broiler Chicks Feed Nano-Selenium, Vitamin E during Embryonic Stage

Treatments	Means \pm standard error			
	At hatching	12 hours	24 hours	48 hours
T1	162.24 \pm 1.91 a	123.64 \pm 1.48 b	106.93 \pm 3.59 b	117.27 \pm 3.89 a
T2	176.88 \pm 1.27 a	136.87 \pm 2.31 a	115.27 \pm 3.42 a	113.63 \pm 1.48 a
T3	100.17 \pm 5.00 b	103.27 \pm 5.02 bc	77.63 \pm 2.53 c	80.37 \pm 1.79 b
T4	92.87 \pm 2.28 c	110.61 \pm 4.58 c	96.01 \pm 0.99 bc	68.66 \pm 1.53 c
T5	92.08 \pm 5.10 c	91.00 \pm 1.00 c	78.15 \pm 3.50 c	78.82 \pm 1.80 c
Significant	*	*	*	*

Note: Significant differences exist among the various letters at the level ($P \leq 0.05$). A negative control treatment with no injection, a positive control treatment with the use of distilled water injection, an injection of a solution of nutrients including vitamin E, and nano- Selenium at concentrations of fifteen, thirty, and forty-five ppm were designated as treatments T1, T2, T3, T4, and T5.

Glucose Sugar Concentration (mg / 100ml blood)

The impact of early feeding broiler chicks with nano selenium and vitamin E on their blood sugar levels while they are fasting from food is seen in Table (4). After the eggs hatched, treatment T2 showed a significant improvement ($P \leq 0.05$) compared to treatment T3, but there

was no evidence of a significant difference between treatments T1, T2, T3, or T4. The T3 and T1 treatments considerably outperformed the T5 and T4 treatments at 12 hours after hatching ($T \ 0.05$). T2 treatment was superior to T5, T4 treatment, and the table showed no significant changes in the 24-hour period following hatching ($T \ 0.05$). No difference also occurred between T3, T2, and T1 treatments.

Table 4. Glucose Level (mg / 100ml blood) in Broiler Chicks Feed Nano-Selenium, Vitamin E during Embryonic Stage

Treatments	Means \pm standard error			
	At hatching	12 hours	24 hours	48 hours
T1	156.12 \pm 0.04 ab	188.43 \pm 2.50 a	150.25 \pm 1.18 ab	203.14 \pm 4.86 a
T2	190.80 \pm 2.56 a	160.77 \pm 1.22 ab	184.93 \pm 1.21 a	207.37 \pm 3.14 a
T3	124.70 \pm 2.45 b	149.17 \pm 1.01 a	152.50 \pm 2.25 ab	150.37 \pm 0.91 b
T4	156.54 \pm 1.57 ab	156.30 \pm 2.12 b	134.56 \pm 4.56 b	135.64 \pm 4.52 b
T5	152.17 \pm 2.98 ab	135.68 \pm 2.49 b	139.07 \pm 3.12 b	139.77 \pm 1.38 b
Significant	*	*	*	**

Note: Significant differences exist among the various letters at the level ($P \leq 0.05$). A negative control treatment with no injection, a positive control treatment with injection of distilled water, an injection of solution of nutrients including vitamin E, and nano- Selenium in concentrations of fifteen, thirty, and forty-five ppm were designated as treatments T1, T2, T3, T4, and T5.

Glutathione Peroxidase and Malonaldehyde Concentration (IU / L)

The effect of early feeding broiler chicks with nano selenium and vitamin E on their concentrations of glutathione peroxidase and malonaldehyde is shown in Table (5). When compared to other treatments, treatment T5 significantly outperformed treatments T4 T3, T2, and T1, but there was no discernible

difference between the T3, T2, and T1 treatments, as shown in the enzyme glutathione peroxidase at hatching ($P \leq 0.05$) When compared to the other trial treatments, the T5 treatment excelled ($P \leq 0.05$) while the T4 and T3 treatments outperformed the T2, T1 treatments. There was no discernible difference between the two treatments T4 and T3, and the treatment T2 outperformed the treatment T1.

Table 5. Glutathione Peroxidase and Malonaldehyde (IU / L) in Broiler Chicks Feed Nano-Selenium, Vitamin E during Embryonic Stage

Treatments	Means \pm standard error			
	Glutathione peroxidase		malonaldehyde	
	At hatching	48 hours	At hatching	48 hours
T1	64.28 \pm 2.50 c	48.94 \pm 1.34 d	14.96 \pm 0.56 a	11.33 \pm 0.84 a
T2	64.61 \pm 1.76 c	56.93 \pm 1.27 c	11.78 \pm 2.50 ab	9.06 \pm 2.63 b
T3	66.82 \pm 2.58 c	65.96 \pm 2.27 b	8.85 \pm 4.10 b	6.63 \pm 1.51 c
T4	70.65 \pm 2.81 b	64.64 \pm 4.40 b	9.86 \pm 2.29 b	6.49 \pm 2.17 c

T5	78.63± 1.21 a	80.83± 1.99 a	4.16± 0.31 c	5.23± 0.32 c
Significant	*	*	*	*

Note: Significant differences exist among the various letters at the level ($P \leq 0.05$). A negative control treatment with no injection, the positive control treatment with the injection of distilled water, an injection of a solution of nutrients including vitamin E, and nano- Selenium at concentrations of fifteen, thirty, and forty-five ppm were designated as treatments T1, T2, T3, T4, and T5

Discussion

The enhanced hatchability in treatments including injections of Vitamin E and nano selenium may be attributed to the antioxidant activity of these chemical compounds Ebeid, et al., (2013) The study demonstrated that nano selenium improves antioxidant status by activating the enzyme glutathione peroxidase, Eszenyi, et al., (2011) Spherical nano-selenium nanoparticles with sizes between 100 and 500 nm Torres, et al., (2012) have been found to have greater antioxidant activity in neutralizing free radicals Huang, et al., (2003), Perhaps the inhibition of oxidative stress by vitamin E is the underlying cause for the successful hatching of the experimental chicks Wang, et al., (1997). Reference Hassan, (2018) shown that injecting hatching eggs with nano- Selenium at a concentration of fifty ppm enhanced a weight of chicks during incubation and boosted the average hatch rate by lowering lipid oxidation and free radical generation. A reduction in the mean thyroid hormone Tri-Iodine T3 Thyroxine T4 secretion may be the underlying factor behind the increase in cholesterol and triglyceride levels in the bloodstream of T1 treated birds. This increase may possibly be attributed to the birds' exposure to oxidative stress induced by fasting and an elevation in lipid peroxide levels. The direct modulation of thyroid hormone synthesis and metabolism by nano selenium and vitamin E may explain the observed reduction in cholesterol levels in the blood plasma of chicks injected with these nutrients. The inhibitory function of thyroid glands typically results in elevated blood cholesterol levels by reducing both the average cholesterol synthesis and the average cholesterol elimination in the bile, Al-Murrani, et al., (1997) & Kazim, Sahin, & Yaralioglu, (2002). The decrease in glucose levels in T5 and T4 therapies

may be attributed to the influence of nano selenium antioxidants on thyroid hormones, body metabolism, and glucose levels, or it may be a result of the drugs' ability to reduce glucose levels Al-Murrani, et al., (1997) & Kazim, Sahin, & Yaralioglu, (2002) & Orten, & Neuhaus, (1982) Vitamin E augments the function of antioxidants within the cell and mitigates the impact of oxidative stress, thereby stimulating the activity of bodily cells, including pancreatic beta cells, and therefore stimulating the production of insulin, which in turn reduces blood glucose levels McKee, Harrison, & Risowski, (1997), Given that birds require elevated blood glucose levels to withstand stress, the blood glucose levels in birds injected with vitamin decreased notably compared to both control and positive control birds, This decrease may be attributed to the anti-stress effect caused by the fasting of vitamin E, which consequently reduced the levels of the ACTH hormone. In avian blood serum, the administration of vitamins is observed to reduce the efficiency of protein degradation, thereby facilitating the production of glucose and resulting in a reduction in blood glucose levels Kazim, Sahin, & Yaralioglu, (2002). Vitamin E functions as a protective barrier to minimise the detrimental impact of free radicals on the body, therefore safeguarding cell membranes, particularly their acidic components. Degradation of unsaturated fats by oxidation can lead to cell injury or the formation of aberrant cells Shlig, (2009). Paolisso, & Barbagallo, (1997) A positive linear correlation has been identified between the concentration of vitamin E in the body and glucose metabolism. It has been proposed that this correlation may be attributed to the vitamin's ability to stimulate glutathione enzyme and raise the concentration of magnesium within cells. Consequently, this leads to the regulation of cellular metabolism, particularly in relation to

glucose metabolism, which is influenced by magnesium. It plays a significant function in stimulating the hormone insulin. The increase in glucose concentration in treatment T1 may be attributed to the birds' exposure to food stress, subsequent glucose sugar production from non-carbohydrate sources, and the heightened glycogen decomposition resulting from increased hormone secretion stimulating glycogen-breaking enzymes (epinephrine, norepinephrine, and glucagon). The synthesis of these hormones occurs in response to stress, with the purpose of fulfilling the body's energy needs during both stressful and fasting situations, as well as regulating blood glucose levels, which serve as the main glucose source for the brain and neurological system. It is evident that the nutritional solution including nano selenium and vitamin E, administered via injection in the treatments, decreased malonaldehyde levels and elevated glutathione peroxidase levels in comparison to the positive and negative control treatments. These findings indicate that the antioxidant nano selenium most likely contributes to these outcomes Wang, Y., & Xu, B. (2008) & Leeson, et al., (2008) & Wang, et al., (2009). Levander, (1986) Observations have shown that insufficient levels of nano selenium lead to an elevation in the generation of free radicals and a decline in the body's capacity to defend against oxidative processes; This condition is often referred to as oxidative stress. Given the reliance of nano selenium on glutathione peroxidase (GPx), which is crucial for detoxifying hydroperoxides and its widely used as a bio parameter for evaluating selenium status in birds, it has been demonstrated that measuring the activity of glutathione peroxidase is a reliable method for estimating the biological availability of nano selenium, upon which glutathione peroxidase relies. The formulation is derived from nano selenium, which serves to save neutral cells and other components of the blood from peroxide oxidation. The rationale behind the enhancement in the injectable therapies The increased hatching rate, lipid profile, and antioxidants observed in the use of vitamin E and nano selenium, as compared to the control treatments, can be attributed to the injection of the nutrient solution into the

amniotic fluid and subsequent ingestion by the embryo during the last third of the incubation period (19 days). This injection triggers an increase in Digestive Tract activity Kadhim, et al., (2021) which in turn enhances tissue protection against oxidation of fats and proteins McDowell, (1989) Consequently, the severity of oxidative stress is reduced. The impact was apparent during the hatching of chicks, as the lipid oxidation processes in nano-selenium and vitamin E injections exhibited a reduction owing to their antioxidant function. The incorporation of vitamin E and nano selenium forms a comprehensive antioxidant mechanism that effectively protects embryonic cells against the harmful impact of free radicals Surai, (2002). The effects of oxidative processes on metabolism are not considered in the analysis of vitamin E and nano selenium Bohm, et al., 1997. The chain of peroxides generated by lipid oxidation processes, which leads to the generation of harmful free radicals for the embryo, is metabolized by vitamin E Karadas, Surai, & Sparks, (2011) & Surai, Fisinin, & Karadas, (2016) and it has reported Surai, Noble, & Speake, (1996); Al-Jebory, et al., (2024); Ajafar, et al., (2024); Salman, et al., (2024); Al-Saeedi, et al., (2022) been documented that Eighty percent of the vitamin E in embryonic tissue is present. Tocopherols exhibit the highest level of activity in embryonic tissue.

Conclusions

The findings demonstrate that vitamin E and nano selenium increased the percentage of hatching, decreased the oxidation state, and enhanced the body's lipid profile. Further research is required to determine how nano selenium affects the physiological characteristics and growth performance of chickens.

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